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Intermediate report on National Consultation Groups

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Abbreviations

LL	Living Lab
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
NCG	National Consultation Group

Executive Summary

The COEVOLVERS project explores how various nature-based solutions (NBS) can contribute to the societal change needed to address the ongoing and interconnected environmental and social challenges. The project focuses on co-creation of NBS governance models, techniques, and practices in seven Living Labs (LLs) across Europe. Through co-creation processes, the LLs together with the COEVOLVERS WPs co-produce actionable knowledge on seven different NBS. Actionable knowledge refers to co-produced knowledge that is needed and used in practice. To support co-production of actionable knowledge on NBS, each LL has established a National Consultation Group (NCG), a platform for diverse national and subnational level actors. The main role of the NCGs is to provide suggestions and feedback on how to make the knowledge co-produced in the COEVOLVERS project actionable across different socio-political contexts in diverse European countries. This deliverable uses the insights from the first round of NCG meetings organised by the seven LLs as an entry point to start to define what actionable knowledge related to NBS could be like. Based on the first NCG meetings, the deliverable identified six characteristics of actionable knowledge on NBS. According to these characteristics, actionable knowledge is: 1) evidence-based and co-produced; 2) easy to communicate; 3) building human resources; 4) enhancing planning and design; 5) enabling policy; and 6) catalysing financing for practice.

1. Introduction

1.1 National Consultation Groups for actionable knowledge

The COEVOLVERS project explores how various nature-based solutions (NBS) can contribute to the societal change needed to address the ongoing and interconnected environmental and social challenges. The project focuses on co-creation of NBS governance models, techniques, and practices in seven Living Labs (LLs), communities of inquiry, across Europe (Figure 1.). In the COEVOLVERS project, co-creation of NBS refers to a process where a group of people including e.g., citizens, experts, researchers, business, and public sector and civil society organisations are engaged into deliberation on shared understanding of needed environmental and social change, envisioning, and developing novel ideas and interventions, and promoting and leveraging the solutions and their implementation in different contexts (Soini et al., forthcoming). Through such processes, the LLs together with the COEVOLVERS WPs co-produce **actionable knowledge** on the seven different NBS (Table 1.). This is done by integrating different knowledge systems and methodologies to systematically understand the design, implementation, and governance of NBS. The aim of actionable knowledge is to fill the gap between scientific knowledge and practice (Arnott et al., 2020) by providing knowledge that is relevant for and needed by policymakers and other potential knowledge users (Sexton and Lu, 2019). This kind of knowledge is considered crucial for sustainability transformation (Arnott and Lemos, 2021).

Figure 1. COEVOLVERS Living Labs

Table 1. COEVOLVERS NBS

LL & NBS name	Why is it needed?	What is it?
LL1: Turku, Finland NBS: Social and ecological compensation	Anticipated loss of green space due to urban densification leads to social and ecological marginalisation.	NBS as rules and principles for social and ecological compensation and appropriating green spaces for the social, cultural, and experiential values of current and future residents.
LL2: Alford, Scotland, UK NBS: Natural connections in Murray Park	People both in rural and urban areas may suffer from loneliness and social exclusion. There may be natural areas that can provide a place for community interaction, foraging and deepened human-nature connections.	A model for sustainable woodland management with strengthened community cohesion between humans and human and nature. Also potential for establishing a social enterprise based on the production and products provided by the area.
LL3: Cagliari, Italy NBS: Committing to diversity	The ecosystems and biodiversity in natural parks close to urban areas are often threatened by a variety of human activities	Increase awareness, participation and commitment of various existing and potential future user groups in the planning and use of the national parks close to urban areas by engaging stakeholders, administrators, and residents to gain benefits for both local livelihoods and ecosystems
LL4: Beskydy, Czech Republic and Slovakia NBS: Virtual networks	Degradation and disintegration of current forests, decrease of biodiversity and water shortage driven by climate change constitute major challenges, accelerating social and economic problems and conflicts over water and forest use between different users	Virtual networks to increase awareness of the risks related to climate change and enhance information exchange, discussion and collaboration for fair and climate smart water and forest management
LL5: Catalonia, Spain NBS: Reducing wildfires by grazing	Wildfires causing damage for both humans and nature across Europe. How to find ways in land-use management that may mitigate the problem.	Different payment schemes for shepherds for grazing sheep in certain target areas, to prevent wildfires and provide work and income for farmers
LL6: Tartu, Estonia NBS: Creating multispecies city	Urban wildlife thrives on ecological quality, while urban nature is mostly valued for human-centered aesthetics and preferences which may not always align with the needs of non-human species.	Nature-based initiatives like community gardens and biodiversity friendly gardening that demonstrate the importance of the cultivation practices that support a variety of local/native species, and empower and support local communities in their biodiversity friendly activities and engagements in cities.
LL7: Pomáz–Kiskovácsi, Hungary NBS: Healing garden	Mental health issues are increasing across societies. There is scientific and practical evidence that green space activities (like gardening) may have positive effects on human health and well-being.	A healing and edible garden in a mental health care institute designed together with the clients and their families, health care professionals, and environment and gardening experts.

To support co-production of actionable knowledge on NBS, each LL has established a **National Consultation Group**¹ (NCG), a platform or interaction space for diverse national and subnational level actors. These platforms consist of 10-15 actors per LL representing i) governmental organisations, civil society organisations, research, and business, and ii) diverse sectors relevant for the different COEVOLVERS' NBS including environment, social, education, rural development, health care, forestry, agriculture, urban planning, and employment/economy (see also Chapter 2.1.). In principle, the NCG members are actors who could play important roles when taking the lessons learned from LLs into policy and wider level practice. The main role of the NCGs is to provide suggestions and feedback on how to make the knowledge co-produced in the COEVOLVERS project actionable across different socio-political contexts in seven European countries. In sum, the NCGs are co-producers and potential users of actionable knowledge on NBS together with other LL members in the different COEVOLVERS contexts. This makes the NCGs as platforms to think about knowledge that may be put into action. This deliverable uses the insights from the first round of NCG meetings organised by the seven LLs as an entry point to start to define what actionable knowledge related to NBS could be like.

¹ In the COEVOLVERS Grant Agreement, WP5 & Task 5.1, the NCG is referred to as National Assessment Panels, but we have renamed them as the original name was found to be misleading. More precisely, the aim of the group is not to assess the LLs, instead the groups provide feedback on all the LLs while also functioning as dissemination channels.

2. First National Consultation Group meetings

2.1. Members of the National Consultation Groups

To become societally relevant and impactful, many NBS require collaboration across diverse sectors and policy scales. Therefore, it was considered essential to engage stakeholders from different sectors to explore and gather their insights from the solutions that are being co-created by the different LLs and the COEVOLVERS project at large. Since all seven COEVOLVERS' NBS were presented and discussed in each NCG meeting, the aim was that each NCG comprise representatives of each sector relevant to the seven NBS. In this way, the NCGs would support not only the work of a single LL, but more broadly, contribute to the design and implementation of all the seven NBS in the different social and political context across Europe. Another criteria for inviting NCG members was their role/knowledge in decision-making, either as a knowledge user or knowledge co-producer.

Following these principles, each LL identified potential members or member organizations in their region or country for their NCG (COEVOLVERS Milestone 11). Table 2 below presents the composition of the NCGs in the first NCG meetings. These may be slightly different from what was originally planned, due to the availability of the invited members and their willingness to join.

Table 2. Summary of the NCG participants representing different sectors and domains with the following colours: Turku, Finland; Alford, Scotland; Cagliari, Italy; Beskydy, Czechia and Slovakia; Catalonia, Spain; Tartu, Estonia; Pomáz–Kiskovácsi, Hungary.

Sector/Domain	Science	Policy	Business	Civil society
Environment	XXXXXXXX	XXXXXXXX	X	X
Social/Cultural	XXXXX	XX		XXXX
Education	XXX	X		XXXXX
Rural development			X	
Health care	XXXX	X		XX
Forestry	XX	XXXX	XXX	
Agriculture		XXX	XX	XX
Urban planning	XXXX	XXXX	X	X
Employment/economy	X	X		

2.2. Preparation, organisation, and reporting

The Living Labs will organise at least two NCG meetings² during the COEVOLVERS project. The aim of the first NCG meetings (M12) was to familiarize the members of the NCGs with the COEVOLVERS project and its seven NBS, and to consult the NCGs about knowledge gaps and needs by requesting feedback on the enablers and barriers of NBS implementation from a cross-sectoral perspective. In addition, the NCG members were asked whether they were familiar with similar NBS as those explored in the COEVOLVERS. WP1 coordinated the planning and preparation of the meetings and suggested a general outline for the meeting. WP1 also provided background and meeting materials for the LLs. An information package on the project and the LLs was sent to the participants prior to the meeting. WP1 suggested the following programme for the meetings that would last 2-2.5 hours:

1. Short introduction of the COEVOLVERS project and the seven NBS (see Table 1. below). Presentation material was prepared by WP1 and the LLs for this purpose, and then given to the LLs to modify to their meeting context.
2. Introduction of participants, including short description of their awareness or experience of the NBS;
3. Small group discussion on three key questions relevant for the project;
 - i. What kind of examples of NBS are used in their field/sector? What kind of NBS they know? Do they already know some NBS or good examples of existing NBS? Do they know of similar NBS as our 7? How did they know about the NBS?
 - ii. What kind of barriers can they identify, particularly from their sectoral perspective, for the implementation of the presented seven NBS of COEVOLVERS in their national context?
 - iii. What could be the enablers of these kind of 7 NBS in their national context?
4. Plenary: reporting back from the group discussions and general discussion.
 - a. reflections and next steps

The meetings were organised in the local language either online (LL Finland, LL Scotland, LL Italy, LL Spain), in hybrid format (LL Czechia and Slovakia, LL Estonia) or on-site (LL Hungary). The discussions were documented, and the LLs reported the results using a reporting template (Annex I). The key findings are summarised in this Deliverable. The following section (2.3) provides an overview of the participants' current knowledge and awareness of NBS in general and on those explored in the COEVOLVERS project. Section 2.4. presents a) barriers and enablers for implementing NBS in different national contexts of our LLs and provides b) a comprehensive understanding of implementation challenges and requirements across Europe at large. Based on the careful reflection of both regional, national, and Europe-wide challenges and requirements helped us to identify and suggest six characteristics of actionable knowledge on NBS (Section 2.5).

² The aim of the second meeting towards the end of the project (M36) is to present results of the project and to get feedback from the NCG to the LL's findings, but also to disseminate their results. In addition to the two meetings, the LLs may organise other activities and more continuous communication with their respective NCGs as they see fit.

2.3. General Awareness of NBS (Q1)

To make the participants of the NCGs familiar with each other and the topic of the meeting, the first task was to share examples and experiences of NBS based on their current knowledge and NBS explored by the COEVOLVERS project.

Overall, the members of the NCGs were quite well aware of some types of NBS in their regions or country. Some of them also referred to examples from abroad. Most of the NCGs were also able to recognize same type of solutions COEVOLVERS is exploring. The participants were typically familiar with the NBS through their work (administration, policy or research), involvement in the civil society activities or as residents.

The NBS discussed were mostly related to urban environment like local rainwater drainage systems, solutions for greening the urban environment and urban planning, and development of ecosystems in urban brownfields. Examples of periurban or rural NBS covered for example restoration of bogs and construction for dams from peat, social farms or farms offering therapeutic services and leisure activities, and NBS that support ecosystem services of forestry against climate change effects. Some of the examples were clearly linked to public institutes (like hospitals, daycare centres for children or elderly people, schools) either in rural or urban contexts.

The solutions covered all types of NBS, like better use of existing ecosystems (wetlands), developing sustainable protocols or practices for managed or restored ecosystems to support ecosystem services or to manage climate change effects, restoration of the environments (e.g. landscapes after mining) or creating new ecosystems e.g. highways for pollinators.

All the NCGs were also familiar with some cases from the social and health sector supporting mental and/or physical health like health paths, green care activities, greening of day care center, health forests, and community gardens were mentioned as well as solutions that support education and learning, social inclusion and sense of community. It was recognized that these solutions could target variety of target groups like citizens in general, people with health problems or suffering from social exclusion. Also, solutions related to policy measures were mentioned. Overall, among most NCGs, the NBS were seen as intersections between ecological, social, and cultural domains, and not purely as ecological or technical ones.

In some of the LLs (LL1 Finland, LL3 Italy, LL4 Czechia and Slovakia), the general discussion revolved also around the topic of managed vs. wild nature (i.e. rewilding): It was emphasized that there is a need to rethink management of environment especially in the urban areas and give more space for wildlife, for example, by leaving or shredding leaves in parks was mentioned as one potential solution. Wildlife could also better support in the forest management practices (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia). Overall, more acceptance for wild and “untidy” environment was called for.

The discussion and especially the broadness of examples also reflected some kind of vagueness related to the NBS definition. For example, in LL3 Italy, most of the examples mentioned represented nature-based activities, like Adopt a tree project, sports in the park, or eco-tuning activities. Various nature-based or nature-related therapies were often mentioned too by many NCGs (e.g. LL1 Finland, LL3 Italy, LL7 Hungary). In Catalonia, the NCGs were aware of some urban greening NBS, but also cases where grazing for wildfire risk prevention and forest management related NBS had been successful (LL5 Spain).

2.4 Requirements for NBS design and implementation (Q2 & Q3)

After introducing the seven NBS to the NCGs, the barriers (Q2) and enablers (Q3) for their implementation in the different national contexts were discussed. Based on these discussions, gaps and needs related to knowledge and awareness, resources, policy, and practice were identified. The results are summarised/presented in this chapter. However, the aim was not to compare the implementation of NBS in different countries, but rather to gain an understanding of implementation challenges and requirements across Europe. These challenges and requirements are mostly related to NBS in general, but examples relating to specific NBS are also given.

Knowledge and awareness

Many of the NCGs identified knowledge gaps that hamper the design and implementation of NBS. These include **lack of scientific knowledge** on i) ecosystem functions, which may lead to a situation where solving one problem creates another (LL6 Estonia); ii) the benefits and impacts of NBS on nature as well as on human health and well-being (LL1 Finland; LL2 Scotland, UK); iii) needs and interests of the local people that could be addressed by NBS projects (LL3 Italy; LL1 Finland); iv) multispecies perspective (LL1 Finland); and v) how different NBS are connected and work together (LL1 Finland; LL2 Scotland, UK). Consequently, the NCGs prescribed more systemic understanding of the NBS and various assessments to facilitate the adoption and implementation of NBS. In addition, more research on NBS-related knowledge and governance gaps were called for (LL2 Scotland, UK; LL4 Czechia and Slovakia).

While public awareness on environmental issues and their importance has increased and this can have positive impacts on the implementation of NBS, **public awareness on NBS** is quite low (LL1 Finland). For example, in Spain, the residents have become increasingly aware of the wildfire risks and are therefore more open for grazing-related NBS (LL5 Spain). In some cases, there is lack of awareness on what the NBS are and what their environmental, social and financial benefits would be (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia). In other cases, several NBS might already exist, but the municipalities/municipal experts are not necessarily aware of them (LL1 Finland). The topic of increasing NBS awareness was discussed by several NCGs. This could be done, first and foremost, by showcasing widely the existing concrete examples of NBS and their impacts for humans and nature (LL1 Finland; LL3 Italy; LL4 Czechia and

Slovakia; LL7 Hungary). In addition, the importance of keeping NBS on the agenda of public and policy discussion in a clear and understandable way was highlighted (LL1 Finland). Education was also prescribed for dealing with lack of awareness on NBS (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia; LL6 Estonia; LL7 Hungary).

Yet, there is a challenge related to **communication**. NBS is still mostly an expert driven approach, and the NBS concept was criticized for being bureaucratic, abstract, and not very informative, which makes it hard to communicate to a broader audience (LL6, Estonia). It may therefore alienate people from the very issues it seeks to address. Furthermore, there are many definitions of NBS, which lead to ambiguity and make the communication challenging. Most definitions originate from the UN and the EU, and their respective projects, but these definitions have not been adopted widely across sectors. Instead, other sectors may have their own definitions. For instance, in urban planning and architecture, the NBS cover all solutions related to nature, which clearly differs from the definitions of projects like COEVOLVERS. (LL1 Finland).

Financial and human resources

NBS are often implemented as part of projects that run for a limited time and focus on designing and setting up the NBS. Therefore, it was not surprising that several NCGs discussed the **continuity and long-term viability of NBS** and raised concerns over financial and human resources needed to ensure the longevity of NBS (LL2 Scotland, UK; LL3 Italy; LL4 Czechia and Slovakia; LL5 Spain).

Many NBS, such as food gardens, need continuous resourcing and consistent labour hours extending beyond the project lifespan (LL2 Scotland, UK). Ensuring long-term financing encourages participation of key stakeholders, such as forest owners (and shepherds), who should receive compensation for their ecosystem services, but often this is not the case in reality (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia). Regarding healing gardens, financial difficulties were seen to create barriers for their implementation (LL7 Hungary), especially in situations where funding depends on health insurance companies' willingness to cover such costs (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia). As for social-ecological compensation (e.g. payment for ecosystem services), the interest of municipalities to implement such NBS may be hampered by subsequent maintenance costs (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia). Suggestions to overcome financial challenges included promotion of public-private funding schemes (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia), targeted budgets for which funding is collected through community taxes (LL5 Spain), and bottom-up funding schemes that opens the budget designing process to citizens (LL6 Estonia), was called for.

In addition to financing, but closely related to it, the success of NBS depends on available **human resources**. It was considered crucial for the long-term success of an NBS that people/actors responsible for the implementation of the NBS are involved in the process from the beginning, i.e. from the planning phase (LL1 Finland; LL2 Scotland, UK; LL4 Czechia and Slovakia). An example was given how the implementation of a good, yet general, plan can go astray when constructors fail to

follow the plan in practice (LL1 Finland). The challenge, of course, is that a city planning processes can last for several years, and it may not be clear who bears the responsibility on different phases of its implementation (LL1 Finland), which requires both, commitment and resources. While projects may intend to create NBS that are self-sustaining, by training e.g. volunteers, the successful implementation of NBS may still require commitment from experts and that someone keeps coordinating the implementation tasks (LL7 Hungary; LL2 Scotland, UK). For example, food garden related NBS project can train volunteers, but it cannot solely rely on them. Instead, the food gardens often need constant attendance by garden caretakers that have the necessary skills, interest, and capacity to maintain the garden long-term, and cannot solely rely on volunteers. Moreover, responsibility for an NBS cannot simply be added as an “add-on responsibility”. For example, it is unsustainable to expect schoolteachers to take care of school gardens during their spare time, e.g. over long school holidays. They may also lack the required experience and knowledge to maintain a garden. (LL2 Scotland, UK).

Last but not least, the implementation of NBS requires expertise across sectoral borders. Currently, however, there is often a **lack of expertise** on NBS. For example, city planners and architects often lack relevant know-how on biodiversity, healthy urban spaces, and green infrastructure (LL1 Finland; LL6 Estonia), while hospital staff (maintainers and operators) often lack sufficient knowledge on the garden therapy or ecotherapy and its inherent possibilities (LL7 Hungary). The NCGs highlighted the importance of education on NBS to improve expertise across sectors.

Policy

Current regulation or lack of it was identified as a barrier for NBS implementation in several NCG meetings. Problems appear when NBS are not explicitly mentioned and thereby encouraged by policy (LL1 Finland). Lack of social-ecological compensation mechanisms for green areas was given as an example. If there are no national or municipality-level rules on how to compensate for the loss of green areas, new development are not likely to take place. (LL6 Estonia). The implementation of NBS initiatives can also be hindered by excessive bureaucracy and lengthy procedures (LL3 Italy; LL5 Spain; LL7 Hungary). In some cases, multiple commands and prohibitions (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia) or the fear of legal rules or their absence (LL7 Hungary) can also hamper NBS implementation. In Hungary, for instance, it may not be enough if something is not explicitly restricted if, at the same time, it is not specifically allowed (LL7 Hungary). Despite the challenges related to regulation, there are also legal possibilities that need to be more thoroughly explored (LL5 Spain). In Catalonia, a “stewardship agreement” through which the landowners delegates management rights over their property to, e.g., municipality, was considered a potential enabler (LL5 Spain).

Another obstacle for NBS implementation is that **environmental values and nature are not prioritised** in urban planning and policy. Instead, **technocratic notions and efficiency** dominate leaving little or no room for alternative approaches (LL4 Czechia

and Slovakia; LL1 Finland). In Finland, for example, new neighbourhoods and kindergartens have been built where nature is totally absent (LL1 Finland). In Italy and Estonia, building renovations in public institutions prioritise functions such as car parking (LL3 Italy; LL7 Hungary), while less attention is given to simple solutions such as vertical gardens and other green areas (LL6 Estonia). Aesthetics can also provide a potential barrier for NBS projects, when the idea is that a beautiful environment is well-kept, curated, sometimes and especially in urban settings exotic (including alien species, flowering plants) (LL6 Estonia). Even when cities are planning green spaces, the projects tend to be driven by visual tidiness (aesthetics) rather than nature (LL2 Scotland, UK). Environmental protection has limited power unless an area has a protection status (LL1 Finland). Therefore, societal discussion on and concretisation of nature values, what they are and how to understand them in practice were called for (LL1 Finland). In addition, aesthetic preferences that emphasize wildness instead of maintenance are needed.

Practice

Collaboration for NBS design, implementation, and management **across administrative levels and borders** can present challenges. Regarding administrative levels, hierarchical city administration may limit the NBS implementation possibilities in urban areas, especially when collaboration within the administration and between the city and other relevant actors is limited and the existing knowledge does not meet the city planning process (LL1 Finland). NBS management across administrative community, regional, and national borders may also be a barrier unless sufficient coordinating efforts, long-term collaboration, and communication are ensured, and shared policies to address environmental challenges that transcend political boundaries are developed (LL2 Scotland, UK). Fragmentation of land ownership and borders related to it present an obstacle for NBS implementation (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia). Dealing with these challenges related to collaboration across borders calls for integrated and collaborative governance models.

The NCGs noted that NBS implementation is hampered by insufficient planning processes that are characterised by **exclusivity, lack of accountability, and unclearly divided responsibilities**. To deal with exclusivity, NBS projects should strive towards strategic engagement and collaboration. Key actors in an NBS project include a project leader who does it for broader social-ecological goals, experts, volunteers and well-defined target audience (LL7 Hungary). Non-governmental organisations can be a key for connecting NBS with the local residents (LL1 Finland). Important potential lies in involving politicians, key city officials, and decision-makers (LL6 Estonia). Effective communication strategies are needed to engage stakeholders and the broader community. Active participation of institutions and political representatives as well as involvement of experts are needed to effectively communicate and advertise projects. (LL3 Italy).

However, it remains less clear **how the inclusion of all relevant actors should be done in practice**. First, instead of a single community, NBS settings often include

several communities, which may have various cultural differences ranging from language to their relationship with nature (LL1 Finland). It needs to be taken into account that participation in NBS may be restricted by some kind of fear of nature. For example, some immigrants might be afraid of the forests (LL1 Finland), while individuals are known to fear certain species such as ticks or bees (LL6 Estonia) and tend to therefore avoid spending time in nature. Second, participation can be hindered by barriers related to accessibility. Spatial justice in accessing public green spaces is often not ensured for all (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia) due to e.g. lack of transportation to the NBS location or mobility restrictions in the area (LL1 Estonia; LL7 Hungary). Third, there is also lack of support systems for those who are not comfortable with novel approach to urban nature (e.g. the elderly, and people with mental health issues). It is essential to ensure the inclusion of these groups that have so far been left out. Without support, individuals in these groups may quickly lose motivation when involved in new practices. (LL6 Estonia). Regardless of the challenges, community engagement and ownership were identified as critical for long-term sustainability of an NBS. Building trust and maintaining a long-term presence/connection with the community is the key. Having the community as part of the process from the start of the projects is essential, but it is also vital to have a long-term strategy of community involvement. It was recommended to have someone provide constant presence and communication with the community throughout the project and even beyond the endpoint of the project to ensure continued impacts. (LL2 Scotland, UK).

New practices related to urban planning have emerged that can foster NBS implementation. For example, in some Finnish cities i) the planners have a common Teams platform for sharing information, ii) they are hiring planning biologists which has enabled to transmit knowledge of environmental protection to city planning processes, iii) technology is harvested for citizen science (citizens collecting information from nearby nature, and iv) social dimension (e.g. benefits related to social encounters in green areas) taken up by policy and planning processes. (LL1 Finland). Other enabling practices include, e.g. i) experiments and possible errors or failures should be allowed because creating a more biodiverse urban space involves trial and error; many practices and knowledge are new, ii) testing zoning experiments on a smaller scale when wild and aesthetically unfamiliar areas in urban spaces create resistance, iii) creating collectively used green spaces in new residential area planning – currently, suburban residential areas are individualistic and monofunctional. Shared spaces would allow people to come together, work together, organize events like communal work, etc., and iv) designing ""meeting points"" or observation points for encountering other species in the urban space, including those usually unnoticed. To provide opportunities to take different perspectives, observe, and meet safely. Moreover, the city could highlight nature in its self-image and marketing – for example, Tartu's nature reserves and protected natural areas could be presented on the website, in tourism, advertisements, etc. Institutionalized, official attention helps reframe the discourse about the city as a non-natural place. (LL6 Estonia).

Table 3. below summarises the abovementioned obstacles and enablers in designing and implementing NBS.

Table 3. Obstacles and enablers in design and implementation of NBS across COEVOLVERS LL

Category	Obstacles	Enablers
Knowledge & awareness	<p>Lack of scientific knowledge on ecosystem functions (LL6 Estonia).</p> <p>Limited understanding of the benefits and impacts of NBS on nature and human health (LL1 Finland; LL2 Scotland, UK).</p> <p>Insufficient knowledge of local needs and interests related to NBS projects (LL3 Italy; LL1 Finland).</p> <p>Lack of understanding of multispecies perspectives and the interconnectedness of NBS (LL1 Finland).</p> <p>Communication challenges due to the abstract nature of the NBS concept and multiple definitions (LL1 Finland; LL6 Estonia).</p>	<p>Increased public awareness of environmental issues, which can positively impact NBS implementation (LL5 Spain).</p> <p>Showcasing existing concrete examples of NBS and their impacts (LL1 Finland; LL3 Italy; LL4 Czechia and Slovakia; LL7 Hungary).</p> <p>Education and awareness campaigns to increase understanding of NBS among the public and policymakers (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia; LL6 Estonia; LL7 Hungary).</p>
Financial & human resources	<p>Limited financial resources for the long-term viability of NBS (LL2 Scotland, UK; LL3 Italy; LL4 Czechia and Slovakia; LL5 Spain).</p> <p>Insufficient human resources for NBS planning, implementation, and management (LL1 Finland; LL2 Scotland, UK; LL7 Hungary).</p> <p>Lack of expertise across sectors, such as city planning, architecture, and healthcare (LL1 Finland; LL6 Estonia).</p>	<p>Promotion of public-private funding schemes (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia).</p> <p>Targeted budgets funded through community taxes (LL5 Spain).</p> <p>Bottom-up funding schemes involving citizen participation (LL6 Estonia).</p> <p>Involvement of relevant actors from the planning phase (LL1 Finland; LL2 Scotland, UK; LL4 Czechia and Slovakia).</p> <p>Education and training to improve expertise across sectors (LL1 Finland; LL6 Estonia).</p>
Policy	<p>Lack of explicit policy support for NBS implementation (LL1 Finland).</p> <p>Bureaucratic hurdles and lengthy procedures (LL3 Italy; LL5 Spain; LL7 Hungary).</p> <p>Inconsistent or absent regulations related to NBS (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia; LL7 Hungary).</p> <p>Dominance of technocratic notions and efficiency in urban planning (LL4 Czechia and Slovakia; LL1 Finland).</p>	<p>Exploration of legal mechanisms like stewardship agreements (LL5 Spain).</p> <p>Societal discussion on nature values and their integration into policy (LL1 Finland).</p> <p>Prioritization of environmental values in urban planning (LL3 Italy; LL7 Hungary).</p> <p>Development of integrated and collaborative governance models (LL2 Scotland, UK).</p>
NBS in Practice	<p>Challenges in collaboration across administrative levels and borders (LL1 Finland; LL2 Scotland, UK).</p> <p>Exclusivity and lack of accountability in planning processes (LL7 Hungary).</p> <p>Barriers to community engagement, including cultural differences and accessibility issues (LL1 Finland; LL4 Czechia and Slovakia; LL6 Estonia).</p>	<p>Strategic engagement and collaboration among key actors in NBS projects (LL7 Hungary).</p> <p>Active participation of institutions, political representatives, and experts (LL3 Italy).</p> <p>Inclusion of marginalized groups through support systems and community engagement strategies (LL6 Estonia).</p> <p>Adoption of new practices in urban planning to foster NBS implementation (LL1 Finland; LL6 Estonia).</p>

2.5. Actionable knowledge on NBS

Based on the first NCG meetings, the deliverable identified six characteristics of actionable knowledge on NBS. Accordingly, actionable knowledge is:

1. **Evidence-based and co-produced.** This entails for example that there is robust knowledge about the impacts and benefits of NBS and better understanding of multispecies relations. This requires reliable, multi-perspective knowledge on problematic situations and potential solutions. Moreover, systemic understanding of NBS is needed to reveal the trade-offs within and between the NBS (i.e. how different NBS are connected and work together).
2. **Easy to communicate.** The study revealed that the use of NBS concept is problematic. On one hand, scientific jargon should be avoided, and on the other, the concept should be clearly defined so that it would not become a buzzword for all environmental or green activities. Concrete examples of key characteristics of different types of NBS could help. Overall, clear communication strategies could help to ensure the consistency and make the NBS language more accessible.
3. **Building human resources.** Typically, NBS are interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral by character. Therefore, their design and implementation call for expertise with knowledge and skills from different fields and sectors. Civil society actors and organisations have potentially an important role in many types of NBS processes. Given the multiplicity of the actors and knowledge, coordinators and mediators are needed.
4. **Enhancing planning and design.** Planning and design of NBS take place in real-life settings in collaboration between sectors and administrative levels. Multispecies inclusivity, justified division of responsibilities, and reasoned accountability are the key principles throughout the process. Experimentation and learning from mistakes are needed.
5. **Enabling policy.** Both integration of NBS into existing policies and new type of policy mechanisms like social-ecological compensation are needed. Another important way to enable policy is to find ways for decrease unnecessary bureaucracy. Overall, policies should prioritise environmental and social values more.
6. **Catalysing financing for practice.** Co-creation of NBS design and implementation should also reveal potential financing opportunities in a given context and encourage diverse forms of funding from public funding to various public-private partnerships. The funding strategies should pay attention to the

continuity of the incentives (e.g. those related to livelihoods), and focus on NBS that are self-sustaining i.e. based on co-evolutionary principles.

Overall, these characteristics illustrate that actionable knowledge linked to NBS is relevant for different purposes. Therefore, it is not necessary that all the criteria are always fulfilled. While the criteria 1. Evidence-based and co-created and 2. Easy to communicate, seem to be cross cutting, the other criteria (3-6) are about applying the actionable knowledge for specific purposes like policy, planning and design, building human resources and creating new type of financial mechanisms. Future work is needed to understand how the characteristics of actionable knowledge may differ across the criteria 3-6.

References

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Annex I: the NCG meeting report template

Name of the Living Lab

Place and time of the meeting

Participants (please indicate how many participants were present at the NCG meeting and which sectors and stakeholder groups (science, policy, business, civil society) they represented. You may add additional comments and descriptions on your NCG members here as needed)

	Science	Policy	Business	Civil society
Environment				
Social				
Education				
Rural development				
Health care				
Forestry				
Agriculture				
Urban planning				
Employment/economy				

Please, report the outcomes of the NCG discussions on the three questions as detailed as possible using the recordings/transcripts, the notes, and/or any other material you collected during the meeting. You can also add quotes (please indicate which sector and stakeholder group the participant represented). Please add also your own remarks and reflection on the discussions around each question. Finally, please indicate the next steps you agreed or are planning.

<p>Question 1: Awareness of the NBS What kind of examples of NBS are used in their field/sector? What kind of NBS they know? Do they already know some NBS or good examples of existing NBS? Do they know of similar NBS as our 7? How did they know about the NBS?</p>	
Your additional remarks/reflections on the discussion regarding the first question	
<p>Question 2: Barriers: What kind of barriers can they identify, particularly from their sectoral perspective, for the implementation of (the presented 7) NBS?</p>	
Your additional remarks/reflections on the discussion regarding the second question	
Question 3:	

Enablers: What could be the enablers of these kind of (7 NBS) NBS	
Your additional remarks/reflections on the discussion regarding the third question	

Your overall remarks/reflections on the meeting including the involvement, group dynamics, needs, attitudes, perceptions etc.	
Next steps: What did you agree on the next steps (next meetings, knowledge sharing etc.)	
How would you like to proceed with your NCG? Complementary participants, topic of the next meeting, knowledge needs?	

Please, name the most notable findings from the meeting (min. 5)	Short explanation why you think this is notable

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